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ABSTRACT

In the countries of Central Asia and the CIS, as well as in developed countries, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) is one of the diseases that is of great importance in the structure of morbidity and mortality of the working age population. The leading role in the treatment of NAFLD is played by lifestyle changes, primarily a change in dietary culture, consistent and gradual reduction in body weight, as well as its maintenance, since without this, effective correction of this disease is impossible using only pharmacological agents. The qualitative and quantitative composition of the diet, the level of physical activity and, most importantly, the regularity of all lifestyle changes are the key to the successful management of patients with NAFLD. This article describes changes in diet and physical activity that have been implemented and recommended by the world's leading research centers.

Key words: non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, diet, lifestyle changes, aerobic exercise.

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JIGARNING NOALKOGOL YOG' XASTALIGIDA TURMUSH TARZI VA OVQATLANISH ODATINI MODIFIKATSIYALASHNING O'RNINI**ANNOTATSIYA**

Markaziy Osiyo va MDH davlatlarida hamda rivojlangan davlatlarda jigarning noalkogol yog' xastaligi (JNYoX) mehnatga layoqatli katta yoshdagi aholining kasallanishi va o'limiga jiddiy hissa qo'shadigan xastaliklardan biri hisoblanadi. JNYoX ni davolashda yetakchi rolni turmush tarzini

o'zgartirish, birinchi navbatda ovqatlanish madaniyatini o'zgartirgan holda tana vaznining izchil va asta-sekin yo'qotish, shuningdek uni saqlab qolish o'ynaydi, chunki bularsiz ushbu xastalikni faqat farmakologik vositalar bilan korrektsiya qilishning samaradorligi pasayadi. Ovqat ratsionining sifat va miqdoriy tarkibi, jismoniy faollik darajasi va eng muhimi, turmush tarzini o'zgartirish bo'yicha barcha chora-tadbirlarning muntazamligi JNYoX bilan og'rikan bemorlarni muvaffaqiyatli boshqarishning kalitidir. Ushbu maqolada jahonning yetakchi tadqiqot markazlari tomonidan tadbir etilgan va tavsiya etilgan ovqatlanishni o'zgartirishga oid parhezlar va jismoniy faollikka doir masalalar bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jigarning noalkogol yog' xastaligi, parhez, turmush tarzini o'zgartirish, aerobik mashqlar.

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РОЛЬ МОДИФИКАЦИИ ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ И ПРИВЫЧЕК ПИТАНИЯ ПРИ НЕАЛКОГОЛЬНОЙ ЖИРОВОЙ БОЛЕЗНИ ПЕЧЕНИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В странах Центральной Азии и СНГ, а также в развитых странах неалкогольная жировая болезнь печени (НАЖБП) является одним из заболеваний, имеющее огромное значение в структуре заболеваемости и смертности населения трудоспособного возраста. Ведущую роль в лечении НАЖБП играет изменение образа жизни, в первую очередь изменение культуры питания, последовательное и постепенное снижение массы тела, а также ее поддержание, поскольку без этого невозможна эффективная коррекция данного заболевания при применении только фармакологических средств. Качественный и количественный состав диеты, уровень физической активности и, самое главное, регулярность всех мер по изменению образа жизни являются залогом успешного ведения больных НАЖБП. В этой статье описываются изменения в питании и физической активности, которые были реализованы и рекомендованы ведущими мировыми исследовательскими центрами.

Ключевые слова: неалкогольная жировая болезнь печени, диета, изменение образа жизни, аэробные нагрузки.

Ayni vaqtda Markaziy Osiyo va MDH davlatlarida, aksariyat mamlakatlarda bo'lgani kabi, katta yoshli aholining 16-20 foizi jigar xastaliklaridan aziyat chekadi, rivojlangan mamlakatlar aholisining 20-40 foiziga ta'sir qiladi [1, 4, 5]. Jigarning noalkogol yog' xastaligi (JNYoX) hozirgi paytda jigarning noinfeksion surunkali kasalliklari o'rtasida eng keng tarqalgan kasallik hisoblanib, jigarning barcha kasalliklarining taxminan 70% ga to'g'ri keladi. Semirib ketish darajasi oshgani sayin bu tendentsiya kuchayishi kutilmoqda [6, 7].

Jigarning noalkogol yog' xastaligi jigardagi ko'pgina o'zgarishlarining spektrini o'z ichiga olib, ular morfologik jihatdan insulin rezistentligi bilan bog'liq bo'lgan, ko'p miqdorda alkogol maxslotlari ichmaydigan (erkaklar uchun etanol kuniga 40 g dan, ayollar uchun 20 g dan oshmagan xolatda) va (yoki) steatogen dorilarni iste'mol qilmaydigan va ikkilamchi steatoz shakllanishining boshqa mumkin bo'lgan sabablari bo'lmagan bemorlarda gepatotsitlarda ortiqcha yog' to'planishi bilan tavsiflanadi [1,2,4]. Ushbu kasallikning rivojlanishi va avj olishiga xissa qo'shadigan xavf omillari etib semirish, metabolik sindrom, 2 – toifa diabet va dislipidemiya belgilangan[2,3,5].

Jigarning noalkogol yog' xastaligi metabolik sindromning jigar manifestatsiyasi sifatida ko'rib chiqiladi, uning avj olishining patogenetik mexanizmlari (steatohepatit, fibroz, siroz) kasallik rivojlanishi kardiovaskulyar hodisalar, buyrak patologiyasi va boshqalar kabi xavf-xatar tufayli fanlararo munosabatlarini belgilaydi. Bu, o'z navbatida, ushbu bemorlarning yuqori o'limiga sabab bo'ladi.

Jahon va mahalliy ilmiy hamjamiyatda JNYoX ni o'rganish va davolashga qiziqish ortib borayotganiga qaramay, samarali maxsus davolash masalasi hal qilinmagan. JNYoXni farmakologik davolashning asosiy yo'nalishlari to'qimalarning insulinga sezgirligini oshirish va jigar shikastlanish darajasini va yallig'lanish jarayonini kamaytirishdir [8], shunda ham ular faqat turmush tarzini o'zgartirish choralari fonida qo'llaniladi [9-12]. Shuning uchun JNYoX uchun har qanday davolash rejimining asosi turmush tarzini o'zgartirish, ya'ni ovqat ratsionining sifat va miqdoriy tarkibini o'zgartirish, tana vaznini kamaytirish va jismoniy faollikni oshirishdir. Odatlar va turmush tarzini o'zgartirish, inson xulqidagi mavjud funktsional tizimlar sifatida, katta kuch va diqqatni talab qiladi. Nomedikamentoz davolash usullarining uzoq muddatli samaradorligi bemorlarning motivatsiyasi va intizomiga bog'liq [6,13,15].

JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda davolanish va turmush tarzini o'zgartirishga rioya qilish masalalariga bag'ishlangan bir nechta tadqiqotlar nomedikamentoz davolash usullarining sezilarli samaradorligi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar mavjud, ammo ijobiy natijalarga erishish usullariga rioya qilish to'g'risidagi ma'lumotlar juda cheklangan. Ehtimol, bu turmush tarzini o'zgartirish majburiyatini o'rganish qiyinligi va uslubiy vositalarning nomukammalligi bilan bog'liq.

Jigarni o'rganish bo'yicha Yevropa assotsiatsiyasi, diabetni o'rganish bo'yicha Yevropa assotsiatsiyasi va semirishni o'rganish bo'yicha Yevropa assotsiatsiyasining 2016 yilgi tavsiyalarida parhez terapiyasining asosiy qoidalari keltirilgan: tana vazni asta-sekin, ya'ni boshlang'ich vaznidan 7-10% ga kamaytirish, bunga kunlik kaloriya miqdorini 500-1000 kkalga kamaytirish orqali erishish kerak; murakkab uglevodlar, o'simlik oqsillari, masalan spirulina, no'xot, loviya, soya oqsili kabilar, o'simlik tolalari miqdorini ko'paytirish va yog'lar ulushini kamaytirish hisobiga makronutrientlar nisbatini o'zgartirish; fruktozaga boy bo'lgan oziq-ovqat mahsulotlarini ovqat ratsionidan chiqarib tashlash; spirtli ichimliklarni kunlik xavfsiz dozadan oshmaydigan miqdorda iste'mol qilish (erkaklar uchun etanol kuniga 40 g dan, ayollar uchun 20 g dan oshmagan xolatda) [1,8,16]. Gipokalorik parhezning eng mashhur variantlari kam uglevodli va kam yog'li parhezlardir. Ikkala variant ham JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlar uchun Yevropa va mahalliy tavsiyalarga kiritilgan [1, 2].

Kam yog'li parhez yog' iste'molini kunlik kaloriyaning 30% dan kamrog'ini, juda kam yog'li parhez esa 20% dan kamini tashkil etadi [4]. Kam uglevodli parhez uglevodlarning umumiy iste'molini kuniga 50 g dan 130 g gacha yoki kundalik energiyaning 10 dan <40% gacha tashkil etadi.

JNYoX da steatozning kechishini kamaytirish uchun tana vaznini kamida 3-5% ga kamaytirish, shuningdek nekrotik va yallig'lanishli o'zgarishlarni bartaraf etish uchun kamida 10% vazn yo'qotish kerakligi ta'kidlanadi.

Intervalli ochlik. Ushbu parhez strategiyasi oziq-ovqat iste'mol qilish muddatini cheklash va ovqatlanish va ochlik davrlarini almashtirish orqali energiya sarfini kamaytirish, yoki oziq-ovqatdan butunlay voz kechish yoki juda kam energiya iste'mol qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Diniy ro'za shaklida intervalli ro'za tutishning keng tarqalishi JNYoX davrida ushbu strategiyani o'rganish uchun haqiqiy imkoniyatdir. Kuzatuv tadqiqotida Ramazon oyida ro'za tutish (bir oy davomida kuniga 15-16 soat) JNYoX uchun TMI ni sezilarli darajada kamaytirdi, shuningdek, glyukoza, insulinga rezistentlik, transaminazalar kabi metabolik parametrlarni va jigar steatoz kechishini ijobiy tomonga o'zgartirdi [17].

JNYoX va semirish o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlikni mavjud, shu sababdan tana vaznining pasayishi bemorlarda sezilarli gistomorfologik va biokimyoviy yaxshilanishlarga olib keladi. M. Palmer tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, semirib ketgan va JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda tana vaznining 10% dan ko'prog'i qon zardobidagi aminotransferazalar darajasining sezilarli darajada pasayishi bilan bog'liq [19]. Boshqa bir tadqiqotda S. Zelber-Sagi va boshqalar tana vaznining 9% kamayishi sezilarli morfologik o'zgarishlarga olib kelishi aniqlandi [20].

Mo'ljallangan tana vazniga erishish uchun parhezni nafaqat miqdoriy, balki sifat jihatidan ham o'zgartirish kerak. Ko'pgina tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, JNYoX ni davolash uchun energiya cheklovining o'zi yetarli emas, parhezda makro va mikroelementlarning modulyatsiyasi juda muhim, shuning uchun muvozanatli ovqatlanish va o'rtacha vazn yo'qotish hozirda eng yaxshi terapevtik yondashuv deb hisoblanadi [11]. Ovqat ratsionining muvozanati va sifatli tarkibi dastlab normal tana vaznli bemorlarda metabolik faol bo'lmagan JNYoX, ya'ni steatoz bosqichida yanada muhimroq.

Bunday bemorlarning parhez terapiyasining asosiy maqsadi tana vaznini normal darajada ushlab turish va tegishli parhezlarning antifibrogen ta'sirini amalga oshirishdir [12, 13]. JNYoX da samarali bo'lgan eng mashhur mikroelementlar rux, mis, temir, selen, magniy, A, B, C, D, E vitaminlari, karotenoidlar, flavonoidlar, filtrlanmagan o'simlik moyining muhim fosfolipidlari. Ular antioksidant, antifibrotik, immunomodulyatsion va lipoprotektiv ta'sir mexanizmlariga ega ekanligi umumiy qabul qilingan [1].

Parhez jigar parenximasida triglitseridlar to'planishining asosiy moderatori bo'lib, antioksidant faolligni kuchaytirishda hal qiluvchi rol o'ynashi mumkin [2, 14]. Bugungi kunga kelib, qaysi mahsulotlar JNYoX rivojlanishi va kechishiga ta'sir qilishi to'g'risida ishonchli ma'lumotlar mavjud emas, ammo bunday tadqiqotlar joyda olib borilmoqda [12,18,24,]. Uglevodlarni ko'p va yog'larni kam, ammo oqsilni har doimgi miqdorda iste'mol qilish lozim bo'lgan parhez JNYoX kechishining yuqori darajasi bilan bog'liq [24]. JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlar sog'lom insonlarga qaraganda ko'proq to'yingan yog'larini iste'mol qiladilar [23].

C. Q. Yang va hammual. tadqiqotiga kiritilgan 999 nafar xitoylik kattayoshli insonlar orasida JNYoX rivojlanishining eng kam xavfi vegetariancha parhez qiladigan odamlarda bo'lgan [3,9]. Germaniyada o'tkazilgan populyatsiya o'rtasida o'tkazilgan tadqiqot shuni ko'rsatdiki, JNYoX bilan kasallangan bemorlar choy, qandolat mahsulotlari, yog'lar, non va non maxsulotlari, nonushta va pishloqni kam iste'mol qilishlari, aksincha, sho'rvalar, pivo, sharob, sharbatlar, parranda go'shti va tuxumlarni ko'p iste'mol qilishlari bilan ajralib turishini qayd etishgan[20].

Bir qator Yevropa va Osiyo olimlari o'tkazgan tadqiqotlar jigar kasalliklarida o'simlik preparatlari va ulardan olingan biologic faol moddalarning foydali rolini taklif qildi [11-13]. Xitoy populyatsiyasida o'tkazilgan tadqiqotda vegetariancha parhez yog'li gepatozning rivojlanish ehtimoli pastligiligini ko'rsatgan edi [14]. 3882 JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorni o'z ichiga olgan Rotterdam tadqiqotiga ko'ra, hayvon oqsillari bilan boyitilgan parhez an'anaviy xavf omillaridan qat'i nazar, JNYoX rivojlanishi bilan bog'liqligi aniqlandi. Ushbu tadqiqotda shakarni iste'mol qilish JNYoX shakllanishi va rivojlanish xavfini oshirmadi [26].

JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda eng afzal sanalgan parhezlardan biri bu O'rta yer dengizi parhezidir [27]. Ushbu parhez O'rta yer dengizi atrofidagi davlatlar aholisini oziqlantirishda an'anaviy yondashuv bo'lib, madaniy, diniy va qishloq xo'jaligi xususiyatlari tufayli har bir mintaqa o'ziga xos variantga ega bo'lsa-da, parhezning umumiy xususiyatlari quyidagilardan iboratdir: ko'p miqdorda qayta ishlanmagan donli maxsulotlar, xom sabzavotlar va yangi uzilgan mevalar, zaytun moyi va yong'oqlarni ko'p iste'mol qilish; kam miqdorda baliq, hayvon yog'lari va dukkaklilar; cheklangan miqdorda qizil go'sht, go'sht mahsulotlari va shirinliklarni iste'mol qilishni o'z ichiga oladi. Ushbu parhezning asosiy xususiyatlari to'yingan yog' va xolesterolni kam iste'mol qilish va aksincha, omega-6 va omega-3 nisbati muvozanatli bo'lgan mono to'yinmagan yog' kislotalarini, murakkab uglevodlar va o'simlik tolasini ko'p iste'mol qilishdan iborat bo'lgan sog'lom yog' kislotasi profilidir [28]. O'rta yer dengizi parhezi kam yog'li, yuqori uglevodli parhezga nisbatan jigar steatozini sezilarli darajada kamaytirishi, shuningdek, insulinga rezistentlik va JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda vazn yo'qotmasdan ham insulin sezgirligini yaxshilashi aniqlandi.

Kognitiv xulq-atvor terapiyasi turmush tarzini o'zgartirishga asoslangan davolanishning muhim jihati bo'lishi mumkin. S. Moscatiello va boshqalar JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda tana vaznining pasayishini psixoterapevtik qo'llab-quvvatlash samaradorligini taqqosladi [13]. 2 yildan so'ng, psixoterapiyadan o'tgan bemorlar guruhida faqat parhez bilan davolanishdan o'tgan guruhga nisbatan tana vaznining statistik jihatdan sezilarli darajada pasayishi, jigar ko'rsatkichlarining normallashishi va uni kerakli terapevtik oraliqda ushlab turish ehtimoli yuqori ekanligi qayd etildi. [12, 24].

Yuqorida aytib o'tilgan Yevropa jigarni o'rganish assotsiatsiyasi va Yevropa semirishni o'rganish assotsiatsiyasi o'rtasidagi konsensusda JNYoX ni nomedikamentoz davolash bo'yicha asosiy tavsiyalardan biri bu jismoniy faolligni haftasiga 3-5 ta mashg'ulot uchun 120-150 daqiqagacha oshirishdir. Bunda aerob mashqlardan foydalanish afzalroq (intensiv yurish, velortenajyordan foydalanish, suzish) [17].

JNYoX biopsiya bilan tasdiqlangan 813 nafar kattalarning retrospektiv tahlili klinik anketalar

ma'lumotlari asosida jismoniy faollik darajasini tekshirdi [25]. Xuddi shunday, S. ZelberSagingning 375 JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorni o'z ichiga olgan kesishgan tadqiqotida faollik darajasi baholandi [26]. JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda JNYoX bo'lmagan bemorlarga qaraganda jismoniy faollik darajasi ancha past bo'lgan. Ammo ushbu tadqiqotlarning muhim cheklovi jismoniy faoliyatning ob'ektiv ko'rsatkichlaridan ko'ra so'rov va anketa ma'lumotlaridan foydalanganligidir.

JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda yetarli darajada jismoniy faollik yo'qligi Amerika jigar kasalliklarini o'rganish assotsiatsiyasi, Amerika gastroenterologiya kolleji va Amerika gastroenterologiya assotsiatsiyasini 2012 yilda jismoniy mashqlar roli bo'yicha ko'rsatmalarni qayta ko'rib chiqishga undadi [24]. Jamiyatning hamkorlikdagi klinik qo'llanmalarida jismoniy mashqlar jigar steatozini kamaytirishning samarali usuli sifatida qayd etilgan.

Bir qator tadqiqotlar jigar steatozining klinik jihatdan sezilarli darajada pasayishiga olib keladigan jismoniy mashqlarning optimal chastotasi va intensivligini topishga qaratilgan. K. D. Kistler va boshqalar tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqot yugurish yo'lakchasida mashq qilish yoki qadam mashinasidan foydalanish kabi yuqori intensiv mashqlarni bajarigan bemorlarda JNYoX rivojlanish ehtimoli sezilarli darajada kamayganligini ko'rsatdi [25]. O'rganilayotgan bemorlar tomonidan intensiv jismoniy mashqlarni bajarish uchun o'rtacha vaqt haftasiga 3 soatni tashkil etdi. Yuqori intensiv mashqlar tavsiya etilgan ish vaqtining ikki baravar ko'payishi bilan progressiv fibroz rivojlanish imkoniyatlarining pasayishi ham qayd etildi. Tez yurish kabi o'rtacha intensivlikdagi jismoniy mashqlar bilan shug'ullanadigan bemorlarda, aksincha, hech qanday jismoniy mashqlar qilmagan bemorlarga nisbatan JNYoX yoki fibroz rivojlanish imkoniyatlarida farq yo'q edi.

Kuchli mashqlar, ularning keng qo'llanilishi tufayli alohida e'tiborga loyiqdir. Ko'pincha JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda aerob mashqlaridan foydalanishni murakkablashtiradigan somatik patologiya mavjud. C. Hallsvort va boshqalar JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarning biokimyoviy ko'rsatkichlariga qarshilik mashqlarining ta'sirini baholadi [23]. Trening jami 45-60 daqiqa davom etadigan sakkizta kuch mashqlaridan iborat bo'lib, haftasiga 3 marta o'tkazildi. 8 haftalik tadqiqot muddati tugagandan so'ng, steatoz, lipidli oksidlanishning pasayishi, shuningdek mushak to'qimalarining insulin rezistentligining pasayishi qayd etildi.

Metabolik sindromni davolashni yaxshilash uchun kuch-quvvat mashqlarini qo'llash bo'yicha 13 ta randomizatsiyalangan nazorat ostida o'tkazilgan tadqiqotlarning meta-tahlili shuni ko'rsatdiki, bu yondashuv semirish, glikirlangan gemoglobin darajasi va sistolik qon bosimi kabi parametrlarga sezilarli ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishga imkon beradi [24]. Shuningdek, visseral yog' miqdori va yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlar darajasining pasayishi kuzatildi [15].

Tana vaznining barqaror yo'qolishiga ovqatlanish o'zgarishlari, ya'ni parhez hamda ma'lum darajada jismoniy faollik bilan birlashtirish orqali eng samarali erishiladi. C. S. Baba va boshqalar o'tkazgan tadqiqotda gistologik jihatdan tasdiqlangan JNYoX bilan og'rigan 40 nafar bemor haftasiga 4 marta kuniga kamida 50 daqiqa davomida aerobik jismoniy mashqlar bilan shug'ullanishdi, tana vaznini kamaytirishga qaratilgan parhez (kuniga 500-1000 kkal kaloriyani kamaytirish) qo'llanildi. 3 oydan so'ng ushbu bemorlarda aspartat aminotransferaza (70,0 dan 41,2 u/l, $p < 0,0001$) va alanin aminotransferaza (104,5 dan 60,2 u/l, $p < 0,0001$) sezilarli darajada kamaydi. 3 oy davomida tavsiya etilgan rejimga rioya qilgan bemorlarning taxminan 45 foizida aminotransferaza darajasi to'liq normallasuvga erishdi.

Yuqorida aytib o'tilgan barcha tadqiqotlar statistik jihatdan muhim natijalarga erishgan bo'lsa-da, bir qator cheklovlar ushbu yondashuvlardan haqiqiy klinik amaliyotda foydalanishga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin. Shunday qilib, C. S. Baba va boshqalar tadqiqotida mashg'ulotlarning 25 foizi qiyinchilik va jismoniy charchoq tufayli belgilangan jismoniy mashqlar dasturini bajara olmadi. Bundan tashqari, natijalarga erishish uchun katta ixtisoslashtirilgan yordam talab qilindi.

Tana vaznini sezilarli darajada kamaytirmasdan ham, turmush tarzini o'zgartirish orqali JNYoX kechishini yaxshilash mumkin, ayniqsa bunda bemor mas'uliyatni o'z zimmasiga olsa. Bugungi kunga kelib, ushbu guruh bemorlarida turmush tarzini o'zgartirish choralariga rioya qilish masalalarini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan tadqiqotlar juda kam.

Oziqlanishning ma'lum bir turiga rioya qilishni baholashning yana bir vositasi xalqaro parhez sifatini baholash indeksi (DQI-I) bo'lib, u to'rtta asosiy jihatni ko'rib chiqadi: uning sifat tarkibi va

xilma-xilligi, yetarliligi, moderatsiyasi, muvozanatlashganligi (inson oziq-ovqatdan oladigan energiya manbalari tahlil qilinadi). Ballar soni 0 dan 100 gacha baholanadi; ballar qancha ko'p bo'lsa, parhezning sifati shunchalik yuqori deb baholanadi [7, 8].

JNYoX ni davolashning medikamentoz va jarrohlik usullari davolashning zaxira usuli bo'lsada, ularni qo'llashning keng tarqalganligi sababi bemorlarning uzoq muddatli shifokor tavsiyalariga sodiqligi pastligi va nomedikamentoz usullarning samarasizligi darajasini deb baholash mumkin. Bariatrik jarrohlik davolashdan so'ng bemorlarning aksariyatida fibrozning namoyon bo'lishi to'liq yo'q bo'lgunga qadar orqaga qaytganligi haqidagi ma'lumotlar bu jihatdan yanada qiziqroq ko'rinadi, ammo qisqa vaqtdan keyin ular yana paydo bo'ldi va yuqori tezlikda rivojlandi [8].

JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarni davolashda metabolik jarrohlik usullarini qo'llash munozara mavzusi bo'lib qolmoqda. Bugungi kunga qadar alkogolsiz steatohepatit bilan og'rigan bemorlarni davolashda bariatrik jarrohlikning xavfsizligi va samaradorligi to'g'risida dalillar mavjud emas. Bundan tashqari, semirishni jarrohlik yo'li bilan davolashdan so'ng JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda fibrozning rivojlanishi va shunga o'xshash operatsiyalarni o'tkazgan bemorlarda JNYoX namoyon bo'lishi holatlari haqida ma'lumotlar mavjud [3, 5].

Xulosa

Jigarning noalkogol yog' xastaligi O'rta Osiyo, MDH davlatlari hamda rivojlangan mamlakatlarda mehnatga layoqatli aholining kasallanishi va o'limiga olib keladigan yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari, qandli diabet va buyrak kasalliklari rivojlanishiga jiddiy hissa qo'shadi. JNYoX ni davolashda turmush tarzini o'zgartirish, birinchi navbatda ovqatlanish madaniyatini o'zgartirgan holda tana vaznining izchil va asta-sekin yo'qotish lozim, chunki bularsiz ushbu xastalikni faqat farmakologik vositalar bilan korreksiya qilishning samaradorligi pasayadi. Parhez va jismoniy mashqlar JNYoX uchun har qanday davolash rejasining asosi bo'lishi shart. Ovqat ratsionning makro- va mikroelementli tarkibi jigar shikastlanishining rivojlanishiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Kam uglevodli va to'yinmagan yog' kislotasi hamda o'simlik oqsillariga boy parhezlar ustunlik berish kerak.

Jismoniy mashqlar, shubhasiz, JNYoX davolashda muhim ahamiyatga ega va jigar steatozi bo'lgan barcha bemorlarga tavsiya etilishi kerak. Tana vaznining yo'qolishidan qat'i nazar, jismoniy faollik kasallikning kechishini ijobiy tomonga o'zgartiradi. Jismoniy mashqlar intensivligining oshishi JNYoX davolashda ijobiy ta'sirning asta-sekin oshishiga olib keladi. JNYoX bilan og'rigan bemorlarda, hatto tana vaznining sezilarli darajada yo'qolishi bo'lmasa ham, ularning yuqori samaradorligini qayd etiladi.

REFERENCES | ЧОҚҚИ | ИҚТИБОСЛАР:

1. Andreev K.A., Skirdenko Yu.P., Nikolaev N.A., Livzan M.A., Gorbenko A.V., Fedorin M.M., Krolevets T.S. Adherence to lifestyle modification in patients with nonalcoholic fatty liver disease. *Bulletin of Siberian Medicine*. 2021; 20 (4): 112–122. <https://doi.org/10.20538/1682-0363-2021-4-112-122>. (in Russ)
2. Byrne, C. D., & Targher, G. (2015). NAFLD: a multisystem disease. *Journal of hepatology*, 62(1), S47-S64.
3. Mathurin, P., Hollebecque, A., Arnalsteen, L., Buob, D., Leteurtre, E., Caiazzo, R., ... & Pattou, F. (2009). Prospective study of the long-term effects of bariatric surgery on liver injury in patients without advanced disease. *Gastroenterology*, 137(2), 532-540.
4. EASL-EASD-EASO Clinical Practice Guidelines for the management of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease // *J Hepatol*. 2016. Vol. 64. P. 1388–1402.
5. Kral, J. G., Thung, S. N., Biron, S., Hould, F. S., Lebel, S., Marceau, S., ... & Marceau, P. (2004). Effects of surgical treatment of the metabolic syndrome on liver fibrosis and cirrhosis. *Surgery*, 135(1), 48-58.
6. Lazebnik L.B. et al. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease in adults: clinic, diagnosis, treatment. Recommendations for therapists, third version. *Ekspertnaya i klinicheskaya gastroenterologiya = Expert and Clinical Gastroenterology*. 2021; 185(1):4–52. (In Russ.)

7. Statsenko, E. S., Turkina, S. V., Ustinova, M. N., & Tumarenko, A.V. (2022). TOPICAL ISSUES OF DIET THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE. *Bulletin of the Volgograd State Medical University*, 19(1), 3-8. (In Russ.)
8. Andreev D.N., Maev I.V., Dicheva D.T., Kuznetsova E.I. Diagnosis and treatment of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: a review of European guidelines in 2016. *Consilium Medicum*. 2017; 19 (8): 8–13. DOI: 10.26442/2075-1753_19.8.8-13
9. Khudoikulova, F. V., Mavlyanova, Z. F., & Mamasoliev, N. S. (2024). NON-DRUG APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE. *Miasto Przyszłości*, 17-20. (In Russ.)
10. Vafokulovna, K. F. (2024). The Place of Reflexotherapy in the Treatment of Fatty Non-Alcoholic Liver Disease. *Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development*, 3(2), 261-270.
11. Andreev, D., Mayevskaya, E., Dicheva, D., & Kuznetsova, E. (2017). Diet therapy as a priority tactic for the treatment of patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *The doctor*, (7), 2-6. (In Russ.)
12. Kazyulin A.N., Shestakov V.A., Babina S.M. The use of combined drugs in the treatment of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *Consilium Medicum*. 2016; 18 (8): 13–18.
13. Andreev, D., Mayevskaya, E., Dicheva, D., & Kuznetsova, E. (2017). Diet therapy as a priority tactic for the treatment of patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *The doctor*, (7), 2-6. (In Russ.)
14. Sasunova A.N., Morozov S.V., Sobolev R.V., Isakov V.A., Kochetkova A.A., Vorobyeva I.S. Efficacy of newly developed food for special dietary use in the diet of patients with non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. *Voprosy pitaniia [Problems of Nutrition]*. 2022; 91 (2): 31–42. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33029/0042-8833-2022-91-2-31-42> (in Russ)
15. Chen K., Chen X., Xue H., Zhang P., Fang W., Chen X. et al. CoenzymeQ10 attenuates high-fat diet-induced non-alcoholic fatty liver disease through activation of the AMPK pathway // *Food Funct*. 2019. Vol. 10, N 2. P. 814–823. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c8fo01236a>
16. Rahmanabadi A., Mahboob S., Amirkhizi F., Hosseinpour-Arjmand S., Ebrahimi-Mameghani M. Oral α -lipoic acid supplementation in patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: effects on adipokines and liver histology features // *Food Funct*. 2019. Vol. 10, N 8. P. 4941–4952. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9fo00449a>
17. Lazebnik L.B., Golovanova E.V., Turkina S.V., Raykhel'son K.L., Okovityi S.V., Drapkina O.M., et al. Non-alcoholic fatty liver disease in adults: clinic, diagnostics, treatment. Guidelines for therapists, third version. *Ekspierimental'naya i klinicheskaya gastroenterologiya [Experimental and Clinical Gastroenterology]*. 2021; 185 (1): 4–52. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31146/1682-8658-ecg-185-1-4-52> (in Russ)
18. McPherson S., Hardy T., Henderson E., Burt A.D., Day C.P., Anstee Q.M. Evidence of NAFLD progression from steatosis to fibrosing-steatohepatitis using paired biopsies: implications for prognosis and clinical management. *J Hepatol*. 2015; 62 (5): 1148–55. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhep.2014.11.034>; PMID: 25477264
19. Gubergrits N.B., Byelyayeva N. V., Klochkov A. Y., Lukashevish G. M., Fomenko P. G. Modern views on nutrition and physical activity in the treatment of non-alcoholic fatty liver disease. *Experimental and Clinical Gastroenterology*. 2018;150(2): 100–109.
20. Tursunovna, E. M., & Abhinav, A. Y. U. S. H. (2024). MIYA FALAJLI BOLALARDA UZLUKSIZ REABILITATSIYANI TASHKIL ETISH USULLARI. *JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE*, 9(1).
21. Malika, E., & Rasulov, J. (2024, April). MODERN METHODS OF TREATING CEREBRAL PALSY. In *CONFERENCE ON THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF SCIENCE IN THE MODERN WORLD* (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 79-87).
22. Egamova, M. T., Murtazaeva, N. K., Halimova, S. A., Usmankhodzhaeva, A. A., & Matmurodov, R. Z. (2020). Game Method of Rehabilitation of Children with Infantile Cerebral Paralysis. *Indian Journal of Forensic Medicine & Toxicology*, 14(4).

23. Tkach, S. M., Yuzvenko, T. Yu., & Cheverda, T. L. (2017). Modern pharmacotherapy of non-alcoholic liver fat disease. *Health Of Ukraine*, (18), 68-71.
24. Vorobyeva V.M., Vorobyeva I.S., Morozov S.V., Sasunova A.N., Kochetkova A.A., Isakov V.A. Specialized products for dietary correction of the diet of patients with non-alcoholic steatohepatitis. *Voprosy pitaniia [Problems of Nutrition]*. 2021; 90 (2): 100–9. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.33029/0042-8833-2021-90-2-100-109> (in Russ)
25. 11. Khudaykulova F. V. et al. the structure, age features, and functions of hormones. *pedagog*, 1 (5), 681-688. – 2023.
26. Vafokulovna K. F. NO ALCOHOL OF THE LIVER DIAGNOSTIC AND TREATMENT OF OBESITY DISEASE MODERN OBJECTIVES //Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 600-605.
27. Daniyal M. et al. Prevalence and current therapy in chronic liver disorders //Inflammopharmacology. – 2019. – Т. 27. – С. 213-231.
28. Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shavkatovna, Rakhimov Nodir Makhammatkulovich , ., & Murodov Shakhzod Tokhirjon Ugli , . (2024). Aspects of sarcopenia syndrome in oncological practice: diagnosis and treatment. *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research*, 6(02), 16–25.
29. Shavkatovna, S. S. ., & Rakhimov, N. M. . (2021). Morphological Verification Of Malignant Neoplasm Of The Urinary System With Multiple Bone Metastases. *The American Journal of Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Research*, 3(06), 145–149.

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9 ЖИЛД, 3 СОН

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